

Shedding the old skin to fly and sing

Portal Admin

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[Science News]

Following is the skin left on the bark of an old tree on a Hanoi street, after a cicada molted and flew up on somewhere nearby.

Photo: A cicada's skin (taken on Sept 2, 2024)

This cicada grew mature much later than its peers since the cicada orchestra stopped playing the music already in late June. We could hardly hear its song due to the noises of a busy road in a densely populated city like Hanoi. But as we all know, the cicada just did what it was supposed to. It would just fly up to some stem nearby and sing the song, even though it is not sure if there's any audience left.

Today, after typhoon Yagi, our preprint titled "Further on informational quanta, interactions, and entropy under the granular view of value formation" did the same thing. Being accepted to be published in *The VMOST Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, the manuscript was shedding its old "skin" to fly and started singing its own song [1].

The paper presents an enlarged definition of value and the information interaction mechanism underlying the forming of a new value. Thus, it manifests an advance of mindsponge theory with the help of quantum physics and information theory [2].

References

[1] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). Further on informational quanta, interactions, and entropy under the granular view of value formation. *The VMOST Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*. <https://doi.org/10.31276/VMOSTJOSSH.2024.0060>

[2] Vuong QH. (2023). *Mindsponge Theory*. Walter de Gruyter GmbH.

